

Africa's Demographic Dividend or Demographic Disaster? A Continent at a Crossroads

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Cartoon: *African rising population*

Source: © Damien Glez, 29 August 2009

Abstract: As the world's youngest region, Africa has the potential to reap a significant demographic dividend, which could boost economic growth, drive innovation, and reshape global labour markets. As the continent progresses through its demographic transition, changes in age distribution, workforce composition and dependency ratios will have wide-reaching consequences for economic growth, social services and development planning. While demographic trends offer an unprecedented opportunity, policy and governance will ultimately determine whether this potential is realised. Supporting Africa's demographic journey is not only a matter of global equity, but also in the interest of achieving long-term stability and prosperity. In Africa, the proportion of the working-age population to the total population is still growing and will peak shortly after 2070. However, Africa's peak worker-to-dependent ratio will be low, which translates into relatively modest potential for rapid economic growth. With few exceptions, average economic growth rates in Africa are too slow and population growth rates too high to enable the continent to rapidly reduce poverty or raise average incomes. Although fertility rates and dependency ratios in Africa remain high, they have begun to decline. According to UN projections, these rates will continue to fall in the coming decades, meaning that by the mid-21st century, the ratio of the working-age population to the dependent population will be higher than in Asia, Europe and North America. Africa has considerable potential to benefit from a demographic dividend. Whether, when and to what extent this occurs hinges on policies and institutions in key areas such as macroeconomic management, human capital, trade, governance, and labour and capital markets. If African countries can continue to build on their hard-won development gains, the demographic dividend could account for 11–15% of gross domestic product (GDP) growth by 2030, reducing the number of people living in poverty by 40–60 million. The continent is set to become a population superpower. Its proportion of the world's population is increasing in an unprecedented manner, especially relative to Europe, and its inhabitants are younger than ever. The youth bulge heading Africa's way is real and, in the next 30 years, it will present African states with economic, social, and political problems the likes of which the world has never witnessed before. This demographic surge is neither a catastrophe nor a boon; it is a wicked problem.

Keywords: [Demography](#), [Sub-Saharan Africa](#), [economic growth](#), [population growth](#), [poverty](#), [Nigeria](#), [Ethiopia](#), [DR Congo](#)

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1. Introduction

Cartoon 2: *Could Africa count on a demographic dividend ?*

Source: © David Pilling, [FT](#) 16 August 2018

[Africa](#) has the world's youngest and fastest-growing population. This could provide a significant [demographic dividend](#), boosting economic growth, driving innovation, and reshaping global labour markets. However, if sufficient employment opportunities are not created, the result could be mass unemployment and social unrest — in other words, a demographic disaster (Cilliers, 2025). As the continent undergoes demographic change, the resulting shifts in age distribution, workforce composition and dependency ratios will have wide-reaching implications for economic growth, social services and development planning. Governments, businesses, and international partners must collaborate to ensure that Africa's demographic shift results in widespread gains rather than exacerbating inequality and instability. Supporting Africa's demographic journey is not only a matter of global equity, but also in the shared interest of achieving long-term stability and prosperity (Cilliers, 2025).

The African population began to increase at the start of the 20th century, when measures were taken to combat endemic diseases, healthcare provision was expanded, and female education was promoted, resulting in a fall in infant mortality (Bankóová, 2021). At the same time, however, fertility rates increased, peaking by the 1970s. It is expected that Africa will account for around 60 per cent of all forecast global population growth by 2050. According to UN forecasts, it is the only region where the population is expected to continue growing beyond 2050 (Bankóová, 2021).

The global ratio of working-age population to dependants peaked in 2012 and will continue to decline, slowing economic growth (Cilliers, 2018). However, in Africa, the proportion of the working-age population to the total population is still growing and will not peak until shortly after 2070. Yet, Africa's peak will be low, which translates into relatively modest potential for rapid economic growth. With few exceptions, average economic growth rates in Africa are too slow and population growth rates too high to enable the continent to rapidly reduce poverty or raise average incomes. However, in a scenario that realises Africa's demographic dividend, the continent will have 418 million fewer people by 2063, but its GDP in purchasing power terms will be US\$1.7 trillion larger than it otherwise would be (Cilliers, 2018).

While fertility rates and dependency ratios in Africa remain high, they have started to decline. According to UN projections, they will fall further in the coming decades such that by the mid-21st century, the ratio of the working age to dependent population will be greater than in Asia, Europe, and Northern America (Bloom et al, 2017).

The outlook will likely be good if African countries can continue the gains already made under better institutions and policies, particularly those affecting the productivity of labour, such as educational outcomes. If African countries can continue to build on the hard-won development gains, the demographic dividend could account for 11–15% of gross domestic

product (GDP) volume growth by 2030, while accounting for 40–60 million fewer poor in 2030 (Ahmed et al. (eds.), 2016)

The youth bulge heading Africa's way is real, and in the next 30 years it will throw up economic, social and political problems for African states the like of which the world has never before witnessed. This demographic surge is neither a catastrophe nor a boon, but it is a wicked problem (Paice, 2021).

Graph 1: Population Growth in Africa 2015-2100 by Age Cohorts (World Demographic & Ageing Forum, 2016)

Source: © Sebati et al, 2017

Today, [sub-Saharan Africa's](#) population of one billion has significantly outpaced Asia's population growth (2.6% vs. 1.1% in 2016, respectively) (Sebati et al., 2017). Africans urgently need jobs. Without new jobs, there will be no demographic dividend. According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), 18 million new jobs will be needed every year until 2050. The total number of new jobs required from now until 2050 is almost equivalent to the entire European population. Clearly, the demographic dividend will only become a reality if African countries invest in the health of their populations. There are many obstacles to overcome. Countries in SSA must integrate policies to combat infectious diseases and non-communicable diseases (NCDs), aligning funding to avoid competition for resources between the two areas (Sebati et al., 2017). The Commission highlights the importance of advocating a people-centred health system approach that can be adapted to the specific needs of each country. Better health will benefit countries' populations directly and act as a catalyst, enabling the successful pursuit of other development agendas, as summarised in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Failure is not an option. A negative outcome would have a detrimental impact on both Africa and the global community. Failing to capture a demographic dividend in Africa would result in millions of people living in poverty and in slums. This would create a restless young population and lead to human suffering and social disruption that could spread far beyond Africa (Sebati et al., 2017).

Africa stands on the cusp of the demographic transition, but good institutions will be needed to earn the demographic dividend (Bloom, et al (2007). Results are most optimistic for [Ghana](#), [Ivory Coast](#), [Malawi](#), [Mozambique](#) and [Namibia](#), which have done relatively well on the institutional side and have significant increases in working age share coming up over the next 20 years. [Cameroon](#), [Nigeria](#), [Senegal](#), [Tanzania](#) and [Togo](#) have the greatest potential for increased economic growth from a demographic point of view, but will most likely have to improve their institutional framework significantly to fully reap the demographic dividend (Bloom, et al (2007).

2. Case Studies

Cartoon 3: *Alternative futures / Good Governance Africa*

Source: © Wangui Kimari, [GGA](#), 9 July 2018

The three most populous countries in [sub-Saharan Africa](#) are [Nigeria](#), [Ethiopia](#) and the [Democratic Republic of Congo](#). Nigeria is by far the most populous country in Africa, with approximately 220 million inhabitants. Ethiopia has 126 million inhabitants, and the Democratic Republic of Congo has 102 million. The following analysis will focus on the demographic development in these three countries.

2.1 Nigeria

Cartoon 4: *In Africa's future there is no place for old and corrupt dictators*

Source: © Glez; [Socrates Mbama](#), 11 April 2019

[Nigeria](#), with a population of over 200 million people, is experiencing a youth bulge. Research on the demographic dividend in Nigeria, covering the period from 1950 to 2050, revealed that Nigeria entered its window of opportunity in 2003, which will persist beyond the year 2050 (Olaniyan et al., 2012). The highest benefits will be accrued in 2032 and 2033, when the dividend could account for over 10% of GDP growth per capita, even under the current performance scenario. However, the demographic dividend will not be realised automatically, and Nigeria must implement strategies to develop its human capital in order to capture not only the first dividend, but the second as well (Olaniyan et al., 2012).

The challenges facing Nigerian youth range from [youth unemployment](#) and limited access to education to a lack of economic opportunities and a high poverty rate, as well as a high [HIV](#) prevalence rate. Contrary to expectations, an increase in the youth population may hinder development if these challenges are not addressed (Omoju, 2014).

Despite its considerable natural resources, Nigeria continues to underperform on many development indicators (Reed & Mberu, 2014). It has failed to invest properly in its current and future labour force, has not developed its oil and gas industries to generate long-term job and GDP growth, and has not diversified its economy. The largest proportion of the population lives in the [North West](#) (24 per cent), followed by the [South South](#) (21 per cent) and the [South West](#) (17 per cent). Since 2003, the [North East](#) region has declined from 18 per cent to 12.5 per cent. In general, population growth is slowing in the north and accelerating in the south. [Kano](#) (in the north) and [Lagos](#) (in the south) are by far the most populous states, with populations of 9.4 million and 9.1 million respectively. Other large population centres (with over 5 million inhabitants) in Nigeria include: [Kaduna](#) (6.1 million), [Katsina](#) (5.8 million), [Oyo](#) (5.6 million) and [Rivers](#) (5.2 million). Nevertheless, if harnessed properly, Nigeria’s population, in combination with its relative wealth, could be a dynamic engine of growth. However, time is passing quickly, and if these investments are not made now, Nigeria will miss out on the demographic dividend and its golden opportunity (Reed & Mberu, 2014).

By focusing on policies that promote [human capital](#) development and [inclusive growth](#), Nigeria can harness its demographic dividend and achieve long-term development goals, with concomitant effects on the economy (Olojede & Oladejo, 2023). As of 2015, Nigeria is the world’s 20th largest economy, worth more than \$500 billion and \$1 trillion in terms of nominal GDP and purchasing power parity respectively, thus making it the largest economy in Africa (United Nations, 2012). While Nigeria has become Africa’s largest economy based on GDP, the economic growth has not been equitable or broadly shared, with almost 60% of the population living on \$1 a day. Nigeria will still have a youthful age structure, which is projected to increase by 40% by 2025 and without effective population policy to reduce the high fertility rate, Nigeria will add a further 63 million by 2050, making it the fifth most populous nation in the world after [India](#), the [United States](#), [China](#) and [Pakistan](#) (Olojede & Oladejo, 2023).

Graph 2: *First demographic dividend, Nigeria, 1950-2050*

Source: © Olaniyan, Olanrewaju et al., 2012

However, the real challenge of development in Africa is not the size of its population and/or resource endowments, but the poor management and politicisation of its demographic dynamics, as captured by census data, as well as the adoption of economic and social policies that ultimately leave the people far behind for whom development is meant (Egharevba, 2017). The failure of political leaders and policy makers at all levels of governance in Nigeria

to pay adequate attention to the generation of quality demographic data upon which relevant policy interventions and decisions are based to address the problems of poverty, inequality, fertility, mortality, youth unemployment and illiteracy negatively impacts the chances of effective poverty reduction, infrastructural provision, security and reproductive health. In order to attain the status of a democratic developmental state and deliver on the much-anticipated 'demographic dividends', leaders must demonstrate political will by investing heavily in human capital and developing a reliable source of demographic data to address the socioeconomic conditions of their citizens, including monitoring and evaluating development plans and programmes (Egharevba, 2017).

2.2 Ethiopia

Graph 3: Total fertility rates by region in Ethiopia, 2000 and 2014

Source: © Admassie, 2011

Vast differences exist in fertility and other health and education indicators between rural and urban areas of [Ethiopia](#), as well as between regional states. It is important to examine these indicators in order to understand where efforts may need to be intensified for Ethiopia to achieve a demographic dividend (Admassie, 2011).

The Ethiopian population is still very young, with little change in the age structure over the 13-year period from 1994 to 2007. However, with the incipient fertility decline expected to accelerate, projections indicate a significant decline in the age dependency ratio over the next four decades (Seifu, Y. et al., 2011). However, the secondary enrolment rate remains low, and there is a significant [gender gap](#) in both secondary education and formal employment. The demographic dividend is not automatic and will only be realised over the course of about two generations. Thus, it can only be realised if the policies and programmes of countries in the early stages of demographic transition focus on the needs, aspirations, and opportunities of a growing youth and young adult population (Seifu, Y. et al., 2011).

Ethiopia has already begun its [demographic transition](#) (Regassa, 2022). To harness the benefits of the [demographic dividend](#), the country must strive to narrow the regional disparities in fertility levels. This can be achieved by maintaining and increasing investments

in human capital (education, health and equity) and by improving socio-economic conditions. By paying closer attention to the priority intervention areas outlined above and effectively implementing supporting policies, Ethiopia could achieve a below-replacement fertility level and reap the benefits of a demographic dividend (Regassa, 2022).

Graph 4: *The growing rural-urban fertility divide : total fertility by residence, in Ethiopia, 1990-2005*

Source: © Teller et al, 2011

Ethiopia is unique among countries in [sub-Saharan Africa](#) in terms of its demographic transitions. It has the largest rural-urban fertility gap (with below-replacement fertility in Addis Ababa), the lowest maternal health service coverage, the highest percentage of illiterate mothers, the largest number of people experiencing food insecurity, and 83% of the population concentrated in densely populated rural areas (Teller et al., 2011).

2.3 DR Congo

Graph 5: Democratic Republic of the Congo Population Pyramid 1950-2100

Source: © [youtube](#), UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs 2019

Although the Democratic Republic of Congo ([DRC](#)) is one of the least advanced countries, its growing working-age population is the key to reaping the benefits of potential economic growth. (Franco-Henao et al., 2018). While there have been some recent economic and social advancements in the DRC, the benefits of its demographic performance depend on the government and institutions being capable of responding to current circumstances with targeted, effective and coordinated policies. Although the DRC is currently one of the poorest countries in the world, this could change in the coming years if the country is able to capitalise on its demographic situation. The main component of the first demographic dividend is an increasing SWAP, which is essential for growth in GDP per capita. In order to promote this, the country must start encouraging a fall in fertility rates. However, many other policies must be implemented to secure real change (Franco-Henao et al., 2018). Urbanization, education, and performance of the economy are three factors often linked to demographic outcomes for the DRC and prospects for a first demographic dividend (Shapiro et al. (2017). The ratio of demographic dependence reduces growth per capita by 5% in the short term and in the long term its effect is weakly positive or 1%. All in all, the DRC will not yet benefit from the demographic dividend in the short term. On the other hand in the long term, it can benefit from it but in small proportions (Mbulo, 2022).

The DRC has one of the highest fertility rates in the world and consequently one of the fastest-growing populations, with mortality rates having decreased drastically in recent decades (Pourtier, 2018). This situation raises the crucial question of youth inclusion in the job market, which is the key to development and social peace. A radical demographic transition occurred thanks to the '[contraceptive revolution](#)'. Nevertheless, public authorities are increasingly aware that the 'demographic dividend' can only be realised with a significant decrease in the fertility rate (Pourtier, 2018).

3 Conclusion

This paper interrogates the potent dichotomy presented by Africa's unprecedented population growth, framing it not as a predetermined outcome but as a critical policy challenge. While sub-Saharan Africa is poised to possess the world's youngest and fastest-growing workforce by mid-century, this demographic structure presents a conditional opportunity, fraught with both promise and peril.

The potential for a "[Demographic Dividend](#)" hinges on a rapid and substantial decline in fertility rates, coupled with strategic investments in human capital. The paper argues that this dividend is contingent upon a critical triad of factors:

Health and Fertility: Accelerated investments in reproductive health, family planning, and child survival to catalyze a sustained fertility decline.

Education and Skills: A transformative expansion in the quality and relevance of education to equip the burgeoning youth population with skills for a modern, competitive economy.

Economic Governance and Job Creation: The implementation of sound economic policies that foster robust, labour-intensive growth and generate sufficient formal sector employment.

Conversely, the paper warns that failure to meet these conditions will likely result in a "Demographic Disaster." This scenario is characterized by a vast, undereducated, and underemployed youth cohort, which could exacerbate existing pressures on public services, fuel political instability, and trigger heightened migration pressures.

The conclusion asserts that Africa's demographic future is not preordained. The trajectory from a potential demographic disaster to a realized dividend is not automatic and requires immediate, concerted, and politically courageous action from national governments and the international community. The window of opportunity is finite, and the choices made today will fundamentally shape the continent's stability and prosperity for decades to come.

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Résumé : *[Dividende démographique ou désastre démographique pour l'Afrique ? Un continent à la croisée des chemins]* En tant que région la plus jeune du monde, l'Afrique a le potentiel de bénéficier d'un dividende démographique important, susceptible de stimuler la croissance économique, de stimuler l'innovation et de remodeler les marchés du travail mondiaux. A mesure que le continent progresse dans sa transition démographique, l'évolution de la répartition par âge, de la composition de la main-d'œuvre et des ratios de dépendance aura des conséquences considérables sur la croissance économique, les services sociaux et la planification du développement. Si les tendances démographiques offrent une opportunité sans précédent, les politiques et la gouvernance détermineront en fin de compte si ce potentiel se concrétisera. Soutenir l'évolution démographique de l'Afrique est non seulement une question d'équité mondiale, mais aussi une question de stabilité et de prospérité à long terme. En Afrique, la proportion de la population en âge de travailler par rapport à la population totale continue de croître et atteindra son pic peu après 2070. Cependant, le ratio maximal de travailleurs par personne à charge sera faible, ce qui se traduit par un potentiel relativement modeste de croissance économique rapide. A quelques exceptions près, les taux de croissance économique moyens en Afrique sont trop lents et les taux de croissance démographique trop élevés pour permettre au continent de réduire rapidement la pauvreté ou d'augmenter les revenus moyens. Bien que les taux de fécondité et les ratios de dépendance en Afrique restent élevés, ils ont commencé à baisser. Selon les projections de l'ONU, ces taux continueront de baisser au cours des prochaines décennies, ce qui signifie qu'au milieu du XXI^e siècle, le ratio population en âge de travailler/population dépendante sera plus élevé qu'en Asie, en Europe et en Amérique du Nord. L'Afrique dispose d'un potentiel considérable pour bénéficier d'un dividende démographique. La question de savoir si, quand et dans quelle mesure cela se produira dépend des politiques et des institutions dans des domaines clés tels que la gestion macroéconomique, le capital humain, le commerce, la gouvernance et les marchés du travail et des capitaux. Si les pays africains peuvent continuer à consolider leurs acquis de développement durablement acquis, le dividende démographique pourrait représenter 11 à 15 % de croissance du produit intérieur brut (PIB) d'ici 2030, réduisant ainsi le nombre de personnes vivant dans la pauvreté de 40 à 60 millions. Le continent est en passe de devenir une superpuissance démographique. Sa part dans la population mondiale augmente à un rythme sans précédent, en particulier par rapport à l'Europe, et ses habitants sont plus jeunes que jamais. L'explosion démographique qui frappe l'Afrique est bien réelle et, au cours des trente prochaines années, elle posera aux États africains des problèmes économiques, sociaux et politiques d'une ampleur sans précédent. Cette poussée démographique n'est ni une catastrophe ni une aubaine ; c'est un problème complexe.

Zusammenfassung : *[Afrikas demografische Dividende oder demografische Katastrophe? Ein Kontinent am Scheideweg]* Als jüngste Region der Welt hat Afrika das Potenzial, eine bedeutende demografische Dividende zu erzielen, die das Wirtschaftswachstum ankurbeln, Innovationen vorantreiben und die globalen Arbeitsmärkte neu gestalten könnte. Im Zuge des demografischen Wandels werden Veränderungen in der Altersverteilung, der Zusammensetzung der Erwerbsbevölkerung und der Abhängigkeitsquotienten weitreichende Folgen für Wirtschaftswachstum, soziale Dienste und Entwicklungsplanung haben. Zwar bieten demografische Trends beispiellose Chancen, doch ob dieses Potenzial ausgeschöpft wird, hängt letztlich von Politik und Governance ab. Die Unterstützung Afrikas auf demografischem Weg ist nicht nur eine Frage globaler Gerechtigkeit, sondern auch im Interesse langfristiger Stabilität und Wohlstands. In Afrika wächst der Anteil der Bevölkerung im erwerbsfähigen Alter an der Gesamtbevölkerung weiter und wird kurz nach 2070 seinen Höhepunkt erreichen. Allerdings wird das Spitzenverhältnis zwischen Erwerbstätigen und Abhängigen in Afrika niedrig sein, was ein relativ geringes Potenzial für schnelles Wirtschaftswachstum bedeutet. Mit wenigen Ausnahmen sind die durchschnittlichen Wirtschaftswachstumsraten in Afrika zu niedrig und die Bevölkerungswachstumsraten zu hoch, um dem Kontinent eine rasche Armutsreduzierung oder eine Steigerung der Durchschnittseinkommen zu ermöglichen. Obwohl die Geburtenraten und Abhängigkeitsquotienten in Afrika nach wie vor hoch sind, haben sie begonnen zu sinken. Laut UN-Prognosen werden diese Raten in den kommenden Jahrzehnten weiter sinken. Das bedeutet, dass Mitte des 21. Jahrhunderts das Verhältnis der Bevölkerung im erwerbsfähigen Alter zur abhängigen Bevölkerung höher sein wird als in Asien, Europa und Nordamerika. Afrika hat ein erhebliches Potenzial, von einer demografischen Dividende zu profitieren. Ob, wann und in welchem Ausmaß dies eintritt, hängt von politischen Maßnahmen und Institutionen in Schlüsselbereichen ab, wie etwa makroökonomisches Management, Humankapital, Handel, Regierungsführung sowie Arbeits- und Kapitalmärkte. Wenn die afrikanischen Länder weiterhin auf ihren hart erkämpften Entwicklungserfolgen aufbauen können, könnte die demografische Dividende bis 2030 11–15 % des Wachstums des Bruttoinlandsprodukts (BIP) ausmachen und die Zahl der in Armut lebenden Menschen um 40–60 Millionen senken. Der Kontinent ist auf dem besten Weg, eine Bevölkerungssupermacht zu werden. Sein Anteil an der Weltbevölkerung steigt in beispiellosem Maße, insbesondere im Vergleich zu Europa, und seine Einwohner sind jünger als je zuvor. Der bevorstehende Anstieg der Jugendbevölkerung in Afrika ist real und wird die afrikanischen Staaten in den nächsten 30 Jahren vor wirtschaftliche, soziale und politische Probleme stellen, wie sie die Welt noch nie zuvor erlebt hat. Dieser demografische Anstieg ist weder eine Katastrophe noch ein Segen; er ist ein ernstes Problem.